

Making Statistical Inference Click for Engineering Students

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Abstract

Statistical inference is a foundational yet conceptually challenging topic in undergraduate education, particularly within technical disciplines where students often approach data analysis with a deterministic mindset. Traditional instruction frequently emphasizes procedural fluency over conceptual reasoning, leaving learners with limited understanding of how sample data can inform population-level conclusions. This study explores an alternative instructional approach grounded in a model that emphasizes active, student-centered learning through data generation and real-time visualization. Implemented in an undergraduate statistics course for engineering students, the intervention was designed to make abstract concepts more tangible by engaging students in constructing sampling distributions using their own data. Observations and interviews indicate that this approach fostered meaningful engagement and helped students develop a clearer understanding of key ideas such as variability, distribution shape, and the logic of generalization. Students expressed increased confidence in their comprehension of core concepts, particularly the Central Limit Theorem, though challenges remained in fully grasping the probabilistic reasoning underpinning inference. Peer collaboration and visual feedback were particularly effective in supporting conceptual development, while technical difficulties with data tools revealed the need for targeted scaffolding. Overall, the findings suggest that interactive, context-rich instruction can connect procedural knowledge and conceptual insight, offering a promising direction for teaching statistical inference in applied settings.

Introduction

Statistical inference; drawing conclusions about a population based on sample data, remains a challenging yet fundamental concept in undergraduate statistics education, particularly within engineering and computer science contexts. Students often struggle to internalize the logic that connects sampling variability to population-level conclusions, especially when instruction relies heavily on procedural or formulaic approaches (Kula & Koçer, 2020). This disconnect between conceptual understanding and computational practice has been widely acknowledged in the literature and continues to prompt calls for more effective, interactive, and contextually rich pedagogical strategies (van Dijke-Droogers, Drijvers, & Bakker, 2022).

In technical disciplines, such as Computer Science (CS) and Business Information Technology (BIT), the challenge is compounded by students' varying familiarity with data analysis tools and their tendency to approach statistics from a deterministic rather than probabilistic standpoint. This study explores an alternative instructional approach rooted in the *Construction Direction Model* (Kula & Koçer, 2020), which emphasizes student-generated data and the iterative building of conceptual understanding. By leveraging real-time data aggregation and visualization during a classroom intervention, the study investigates how engineering students develop an understanding of statistical inference through hands-on, interactive learning experiences.

Theoretical Foundations: The difficulties students face in learning statistical inference are well documented. A central issue is the abstract nature of inference itself; using incomplete sample information to make claims about a larger population. According to Kula and Koçer (2020), this challenge arises partly from the conceptual misalignment between how inference is constructed in practice (based on random sampling and variability) and how it is often presented in instruction (as a fixed application of pre-defined procedures). They argue that instructional approaches must prioritize conceptual construction over mechanical application, proposing the *Construction Direction Model* as a means to bridge this gap. This model encourages students to generate their own data, construct sampling distributions, and reflect on variability in an exploratory and inductive fashion.

Complementing this approach, van Dijke-Droogers et al. (2022) propose that the introduction of statistical inference can be greatly enhanced through repeated sampling activities and the use of digital tools for statistical modelling. They emphasize the educational value of interactive representations, such as simulations of repeated samples drawn from a “black box”, in helping students intuitively grasp key inferential ideas. These forms of engagement provide a natural segue into more formal topics like hypothesis testing, supporting a trajectory of increasingly sophisticated reasoning.

Other scholars have similarly underscored the importance of informal reasoning as a foundation for understanding statistical inference in the undergraduate level. Blomberg (2024) stresses that inference should be recognized as a central concept in school-level statistics education, which necessitates careful curriculum design and evaluation. De Vetten, Keijzer, and Schoonenboom (2023) further highlight that pre-service teachers, and by extension, undergraduate students, benefit when instruction focuses on the logic of generalization from sample to population, rather than on symbolic manipulation alone. Their findings reinforce the idea that fostering inferential reasoning requires opportunities for learners to engage directly with data, test assumptions, and reflect on their interpretations.

Together, these studies suggest that conceptually grounded, interactive, and contextually meaningful instruction is critical to advancing students’ understanding of statistical inference. The present study aligns with this body of research by implementing the *Construction Direction Model* in an undergraduate statistics course for engineering students, with the goal of investigating how such an approach can make inference “click” in both conceptual and practical terms.

Methodology

This study adopts a Design-Based Research (DBR) methodology to investigate how the *Construction Direction Model* can support engineering students in developing a conceptual understanding of statistical inference. Given the complex, context-dependent nature of learning statistical inference and the need to improve both theory and instructional practice, DBR offers an appropriate and flexible framework. It enables iterative design, implementation, and analysis of educational interventions within

authentic classroom settings, allowing researchers to examine not only the effectiveness of the intervention but also the process by which learning improvements are achieved (Anderson & Shattuck, 2012). The research was conducted during a scheduled statistics course at the University of Twente, with second-year Computer Science (CS) and Business Information Technology (BIT) students. A total of 63 students attended the intervention, which was based on voluntary sign-up. The intervention took place during Week 3 of the course module, following the students' prior instruction in fundamental statistical concepts such as hypothesis testing, error types, and sampling distributions. The lesson was implemented after students had covered the foundations (e.g., random sampling, sample statistics) and just before the more technical sections on population mean testing under unknown variance.

The instructional design was guided by the *Construction Direction Model* (Kula & Koçer, 2020), which emphasizes the active construction of statistical concepts through student-generated data. Prior to class, students were asked to analyze a small given dataset by calculating the sample mean and constructing a histogram. During the intervention/session, students calculated sample means and submitted their results through Microsoft Forms. A histogram of these sample means was generated and displayed in real-time, illustrating the emergence of the sampling distribution and reinforcing core ideas from the Central Limit Theorem.

The intervention followed a detailed lesson plan, which included both pre-class tasks (data preparation and individual sample analysis) and in-class activities (interactive comparisons of population, sample, and sampling distribution histograms; guided discussions; and application of inferential reasoning). Digital tools, including Microsoft Forms, facilitated data submission and visualization. Throughout the session, emphasis was placed on peer discussion and teacher-guided interpretation of emerging statistical patterns.

The data collection process was multifaceted and aligned with the DBR principle of triangulation. First, classroom interaction data were gathered through Microsoft Forms and teacher observations. A colleague with expertise in education observed the session to document student engagement, instructional pacing, and fidelity to the intended design. The lesson plan itself was reviewed in advance by four colleagues (two statisticians and two educational experts) to ensure both content accuracy and pedagogical soundness. In addition, two follow-up semi-structured interviews were conducted with student participants to elicit deeper insights into their understanding, experiences, and perceived challenges around two months after the implementation. These interviews were conducted with informed consent and recorded for later analysis. Ethical approval for the study was obtained through the university's internal review process.

The analysis phase involves a qualitative evaluation of student responses (e.g., explanations, interpretations during discussion), interview transcripts, and observational notes. Preliminary trends suggest increased student engagement and improved conceptual clarity regarding the behavior of sample means, variability, and the logic behind statistical inference. Particular attention is being paid to students' ability to connect sampling

variability to inferential conclusions, and to recognize the role of randomness and distribution shape in estimating population parameters.

Findings and Discussion

Student Engagement and Focus: The voluntary nature of the implementation led to the participation of students who were inherently more motivated. Classroom observations and the teacher's diary indicated that student engagement was significantly higher compared to prior lecture-based or traditional Q&A sessions. Students were notably more attentive during the data collection and histogram analysis phases. According to the teacher, students asked more conceptually rich questions than in previous years, showing deeper engagement with the material.

When students submitted their sample means via Microsoft Forms (see Figure 1) and viewed the live sampling distribution histogram (see Figure 2), they displayed sustained focus. Peer chatter decreased notably during this stage, replaced by intense observation and interest in how the distribution evolved. These behaviors align with the observer's notes, which confirmed heightened attentiveness and student participation, particularly when the teacher referred to the realism of incomplete data and the importance of not fabricating responses.

Figure 1. Examples of student-submitted sample histograms.

Figure 1. Population histogram and the resulting sampling distribution with displayed sample mean values.

Evidence of Conceptual Understanding: Analysis of students' submissions showed that nearly all students successfully calculated their sample means, indicating procedural fluency. However, interviews revealed some difficulties related to the use of Excel, particularly among BIT students. While all students produced accurate sample means and

histograms, BIT students initially struggled more with constructing histograms, a challenge resolved through peer support during the session. Students from both CS and BIT backgrounds worked together, though the CS students demonstrated greater technical ease. The differentiated technical skill levels did not hinder the lesson, due to peer-led scaffolding and the collaborative structure.

Both interviews and classroom interaction suggested that the session supported students in forming conceptual links. One student remarked during the session, “*I really understand the CLT now, I thought I understood it but I think now I really really get it.*” The observer noted spontaneous peer discussion following more complex questions and suggested allowing more time for this interaction to evolve. This collaborative environment also fostered better engagement, with students appreciating the teacher’s continuous encouragement and responsiveness.

Interview Insights: In post-session interviews conducted more than two months later, students were still able to articulate the concept of the CLT, despite minor omissions in technical language. They expressed appreciation for using their own data in the lesson, which personalized and contextualized the content.

However, the interviews revealed lingering difficulty in understanding why sample statistics can inform us about population parameters. This appeared tied to a weak grasp of cumulative distribution functions (CDFs), particularly the role of the normal distribution in inference.

Students also struggled to interpret the probabilistic nature of the sampling distribution. They asked insightful questions during the session about the distance ‘*d*’ between their sample means and the population mean, reflecting their effort to grasp the probabilistic nature, variability and uncertainty in sampling. These conceptual struggles were productive, highlighting where future instruction might be deepened.

Discussion: The implementation of the *Construction Direction Model* provided a clear pedagogical advantage in bridging the gap between theoretical and applied statistical reasoning. By constructing their own sample statistics and visually experiencing the emergence of the sampling distribution, students moved beyond abstract or hypothetical explanations.

This hands-on approach helped build conceptual understanding of the CLT and addressed key issues identified in the literature (e.g., Tintle et al., 2015), especially regarding students' misconceptions about variability and inference. Rather than memorizing statistical formulas, students engaged directly with the process of sampling, contributing to a more embodied understanding.

The interactive design—using students’ own data, real-time histogram visualization, and peer collaboration—was highly effective. One area for improvement lies in scaffolding students' technical skills in Excel, particularly for those less familiar. Additionally, varying sample sizes (e.g., $n=50$, $n=100$) could further enrich understanding of distributional changes and reinforce the CLT.

The classroom observer reported no evidence of the Hawthorne effect influencing student behavior. On the contrary, students appeared genuinely engaged, and classroom dynamics reflected authentic participation.

Future lessons would benefit from additional supports for visualizing abstract statistical concepts like the CDF, and perhaps incorporating interactive tools to gather anonymous feedback about student difficulties during class.

References

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